

A STUDY ON THE ATTITUDE OF HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARDS INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Introduction:

Education is an activity or a process which transforms the behaviour of a person from 'instinctive behaviour' to 'human behaviour'. It makes a man rational, self-reliant, self-conscious, civilized, sociable and harmonious. It includes good habits in man and makes his life systematic, develop aspirations, ambitions, desires in him makes him powerful and paves the way for one's development. People devoid of Education get easily manipulated by ill meaning leaders and believe them whatever they told. Education measured as the best mean to nourish our basic instincts and in developing all aspects of human life. In almost all country, children and adults are being excluded from formal Educational together; some of them who go to school do not complete. They are slowly and intentionally pushed out of the school system because schools are not sensitive to their learning styles and backgrounds. Perspectives on the disabled and on their Education have been changing. It also brings in sympathy, compassion and humanitarian approach towards disability. But these children need support and opportunities instead of compassion and sympathy. This perspective on disability gives foundation for a new form of Education that would neither require a child to get isolated nor fit in the regular school system not designed for her/him, hence, gives the origin of the concept of Inclusive Education, where the school responds to the ability of the child. "Inclusion is seen as a process of addressing and responding to the variety of all learners through increasing participation in learning, cultures and communities, and reducing exclusion within and from Education. (UNESCO, 2005).

The goal of Education for children with or without special needs is to prepare them for a happy, productive and useful civil life. Children with disabilities had been receiving Education in separate schools called special schools. Special schools are opened for different type of disabilities. It has now been advocated that disabled children should be educated in main stream schools in the company of non-disabled peers. The fundamental principle of the inclusive schools is that "all children should learn together, wherever possible, regardless of any difficulties or differences they may have. Inclusive schools must recognize and respond to diverse needs of their students, accommodating both different styles and rates of learning and ensuring quality of Education through appropriate curricula, organizational arrangements, teaching strategies, resource use and partnerships with their communities" (UNESCO,1994). Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA, 2002) ensures that every child with special needs, irrespective of the kind, category and degree of disability, is provided meaningful and quality Education.

Inclusive Education:

The concept of inclusive schooling has been clearly spelt out in the Salamanca Statement and Framework of Action of Special Needs Education (1994). Inclusive Education, as an approach, seeks to address the learning needs of all children, those who are vulnerable to marginalization and exclusion. It implies all learners with or without disabilities being able to learn together through access to common school provisions, schools, and community educational setting with an appropriate network of support services. This is possible only in a flexible Education system that assimilates the needs of a diverse range of learners and adapts itself to meet these needs. It aims at all stake holders in the system (learners, parents, community, teachers, administrators, and policy makers) to be comfortable with diversity and see it as a challenge rather than a problem. The Children Right to Free and Compulsory Education Act or Right to Education Act (RTE) 2009 provides for the modalities of the provision of free and compulsory education for children between age of six and fourteen in India under Article 21A of the Indian Constitution. After the RTE Act, India has become one of 135 countries to make Education a fundamental right of every child.

Need of the Study:

Children with disabilities are nervous and feel uncomfortable while studying in general class room settings. During various activities, this group of children become a victim of abused words and center of laugh by normal children which directly affects their moral, and consider as a big obstacle in creating common learning environment. Even normal children also feel it difficult to initiate friendship with disabled children because of negative perception of general school students (Das & Kattumuri, 2011). Teachers are still having negative attitude towards the inclusion of students with disabilities, they are still not having proper awareness regarding Inclusive Education. Whereas, Hashim et al. (2014) found that there is no significant relationship

between understanding and attitudes of teachers towards Inclusive Education.

All children are special in one way or another. A teacher in the class room is confronted with the job of identifying these needs, to assess their precise nature and to provide learning experiences accordingly. Therefore, teachers are the right persons to understand the children because they are the role model for the students and society makers. Thus, this study attempts to find out the Attitude of Teachers towards Inclusive Education.

Objectives of the Study:

- To find out significant difference, if any, between the Attitude of Male and Female high school teachers towards Inclusive Education.
- To find out significant difference, if any, between the Attitude of the high school teachers who belong to Above 40 years old and Below 40 years old towards Inclusive Education.
- To find out the significant difference between Married high school teachers and Unmarried high school teachers in their Attitude towards Inclusive Education

Hypotheses of the Study:

- There is no significant difference between the Attitude of Male and Female high school teachers towards Inclusive Education.
- There is no significant difference between the Attitude of the high school teachers who belong to Above 40 years old and Below 40 years towards Inclusive Education.
- There is no significant difference between Married high school teaches and Unmarried high school teachers in their Attitude towards Inclusive Education.

Delimitations of the Study:

- This study was conducted within the Tiruppur District.
- This study was limited to 200 high school (Those are handling high school level) teachers only.

Review of the Literature:

Desombre *et. al.* (2018) conducted a study on French Teachers' General Attitude toward Inclusion: The Indirect Effect of Teacher Efficacy. Results confirm that general teachers have comparatively less positive attitude toward inclusion than special Education teachers. Ewing *et al.* (2018) conducted a study on Teachers' Attitudes towards Inclusive Education. This study dealt with Teachers' attitudes towards Inclusive Education affect its successful implementation with in main stream schools. Low *et al.* (2018) conducted a study on "Pre-Service Teachers' Attitude towards Inclusive Education for Students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in Malaysia". The finding of the study revealed that the special Education pre-service teachers were less in favour of the total inclusion of students with ASD in the mainstream, when compared with the Non-special Education pre-service teachers.

Stemberger and Kiswarday (2017) conducted a study on "Attitude towards Inclusive Education: The Perspective of Slovenian Preschool and Primary School Teachers". The results revealed that both pre-school and primary school teachers are in favour of inclusion on all three levels. However, additional analyses to indicated that compared to primary school teachers, preschool teachers express more positive attitude on cognitive level.

Kundu and Rice (2019) conducted a study on Indian Educators perception of their inclusion implementation practices. The findings revealed that head teachers and teachers perceived that their schools were not implementing inclusive. Kaur (2018) conducted a study on "Perspective of teachers towards Inclusive Education in relation to organizational climate, professional commitment and curricular adaptation in government schools of Chandigarh". The results revealed that Special Educators were more dedicated to their teaching profession as compared to General Teachers in inclusive schools. Mishra *et.al.* (2018) conducted a study on "Perception of School Teachers towards Inclusive Education System in Urban Jodhpur". The study focused on factors involving to this perception. It revealed positive attitude for the Inclusive Education among teachers in urban schools.

Method of the Study:

The investigator used survey method for this investigation. This type of descriptive research uses the questionnaire as research tool for data collection.

Sample for the Study:

The investigator has selected fifteen schools in Tiruppur District. For the present study 200 high school teachers were selected from fifteen schools randomly. The sample includes both male and female teachers.

Variables of the Study:

Gender, Age of the teacher and Marital Status are taken into account for the present study from the 200 samples taken from Tiruppur District.

Tool Used for the Study:

In order to carry out any type of investigation; data must be gathered with the help of the certain instruments or devices. The selection of suitable instruments or tools is vital importance of successful research. For the present investigation, the investigator used. Teacher's Attitude towards Inclusion Scale which consists of 27 statements by Deng Meng (2008).

Administration of the Tool:

The investigator sought permission from the head masters in the irrespective schools and approached the teachers and was assured that their responses would be kept confidential and used for research purpose only. Sufficient copies of the revised tool were prepared and distributed to a random sample of high school teachers. Clear instruction was given as to enable them to give their responses meaningfully. The teacher’s doubts were clarified then and there and the filled-up tools were collected by the investigator.

Scheme of Analysis:

Descriptive analysis and differential analysis were used for analyzing the data. The t-test was used to find out the significant differences, if any, between the mean scores of different groups of variables used in the study.

Table 1.1: Difference between Male and Female High School Teachers towards Inclusive Education

Gender	N	Mean	SD	T	df	Significance
Male	68	82.07	8.52	2.2	198	Sig.
Female	132	85.11	10.47			

* Significance at 0.05; Level: 1.97

The above table 1.1 reveals that the mean score of male teachers is (82.07) where N=68, and the mean score of female teachers is (85.11) where N= 132. The above table also indicates that the obtained ‘t’ value (2.2) which is greater than the table value (1.97). Hence the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference between the Attitude of Male and Female high school teachers towards Inclusive Education” is rejected.

Table 1.2: Attitude of High School Teachers above 40 years old and below 40 years old towards Inclusive Education

Age	N	Mean	SD	T	df	Significance
Above 40	89	84.34	10.33	0.33	198	N.S.
Below 40	111	83.86	9.64			

* Significance at 0.05 Level 1.97

The above table 1.2 reveals that the mean score of Above 40 age group High School teachers is (84.34) where N=89, and the mean score of Below 40 age group teachers is (83.86) where N=111. The above table also indicates that the obtained ‘t’-value (0.33) is less than the table value (1.97). Hence the null hypothesis Attitude of high school teachers Above 40 years old and Below 40 years old towards Inclusive Education is accepted.

Table 1.3: Difference between Married and Unmarried High School Teachers towards Inclusive Education

Married Status	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	Significance
Married	123	83.01	9.52	2.4	192	Sig..
Unmarried	67	80.07	11.47			

* Significance at 0.05 Level

The above table 1.3 reveals that the mean score of married teachers is (83.01) where N=68, and the mean score of unmarried teachers is (80.07) where N= 132. The above table also indicates that the obtained ‘t’ value (2.4) which is greater than the table value (1.97). Hence the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference between Married high school teaches and Unmarried high school teachers in their Attitude towards Inclusive Education” is rejected.

Findings of the Study:

- The high school teachers have high positive attitude towards Inclusive Education.
- The female high school teachers have more positive attitude than the male teachers.
- The teachers who belong to above 40 years old have more positive attitude than teachers who belong to below 40 years old.
- There is significant difference between the attitude of male and female high school teachers towards Inclusive Education.
- There is no significant difference between the attitude of the high school teachers who belong to above 40 years old and the high school teachers who belong to below 40 years old towards Inclusive Education.
- There is significant difference between Married high school teachers and Unmarried high school teachers in their Attitude towards Inclusive Education

Educational Implications:

Teachers’ attitude is vital to analyse for implementing of any kind challenges in the educational field. Teacher is considered as the single most important asset to implement any educational programme effectively at grass root level, and the achievement of the students directly correlated with the efficiency and quality of a teacher. An effective teacher is one, who can create a flexible classroom environment for their students where all learners are able to achieve as according to their unique learning needs. The professional effectiveness as well as the growth of teachers broadly depends on their attitudes. Positive attitudes towards an event/ task move teachers to do it in a positive or effective way for better results.

- Inclusive training should be given to school teachers for understanding the needs of children with disabilities
- In-service Training in Special Education should be given to high school teachers to develop positive attitude and to update the teaching strategies.
- Inclusive Education should be included in the curriculum of Teacher Education.
- Awareness about Inclusive Education should be given to parents, administrators and other stake holders.

Conclusion:

Inclusive Education is very essential for attaining the goal of Equality of Education for all. Attitude of teachers towards Inclusive Education is necessary for implementing the Inclusive Education. This study reveals that the High School Teachers have high positive Attitude towards Inclusive Education.

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